

THE IMPORTANCE OF BANK PROFITABILITY IN ENSURING FINANCIAL STABILITY

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Abstract: *This article identifies and evaluates the essence and specific characteristics of financial stability in banks. The scientific studies of local and foreign scholars on this category have been reviewed and systematized. The perspectives of scholars regarding capital adequacy and liquidity indicators in ensuring financial stability have been analyzed. Based on the research, scientific conclusions and recommendations have been developed.*

Keywords: *bank stability, capital adequacy, liquidity, insolvency, asset quality, capital and asset profitability.*

Introduction.

In many studies, profitability has been explained through various approaches, but its essence lies in expressing the level of financial return obtained per unit of invested resources. In banks, profitability has two perspectives: it serves as an indicator of the efficiency of capital and asset utilization. On one hand, it allows for assessing the income generated from risk-weighted assets, while on the other, it reflects how effectively a bank utilizes its capital.

It is noteworthy that the efficiency of a bank's capital is closely tied to the stability of macroeconomic policies. Numerous foreign studies confirm that asset profitability is strongly correlated with economic growth. In Uzbekistan, trends indicate that the efficiency of bank capital is more dependent on internal factors. Overall, the efficiency of a bank's capital develops in relation to both macroeconomic and microeconomic factors. Therefore, considering all factors affecting asset efficiency is crucial for ensuring the financial stability of banks.

Literature Review

During our research, we focused on analyzing the scientific conclusions from foreign studies aimed at evaluating the efficiency of banks' financial operations. We aim to systematize the theoretical impact of asset profitability on banks' financial stability based on scientific conclusions found in the literature. Numerous Uzbek scholars have produced works on asset profitability and their effective management, some of which we will review below.

DSc H. Rahmatov, in his doctoral dissertation, formulates scientific conclusions aimed at increasing the efficiency of commercial bank assets. He analyzes the interrelations between the concepts of "asset efficiency (profitability)," "asset quality," and "asset liquidity." According to him, diversification, evaluation, and monitoring are critical for ensuring profitability through asset efficiency. Based on his research, he proposes a model for enhancing commercial bank asset efficiency, divided into three levels [1].

M. Mo'minova focuses on formulating scientific conclusions to ensure efficiency in managing the active and passive operations of commercial banks. She highlights scientific approaches to increasing asset efficiency through the development of innovative activities. According to her, reducing the share of non-income-generating assets in the total asset portfolio and focusing on project investments during diversification are essential. She also emphasizes the

need to consider regional economic characteristics in regional credit programs to enhance asset efficiency [2].

L. Muradova, in her doctoral dissertation, focuses on developing scientific approaches to increasing the profitability of assets. She emphasizes diversification to enhance asset profitability and proposes quantitative criteria for diversification. Specifically, she suggests that the share of a bank's credit portfolio in any single sector should not exceed 25%. She also notes the importance of aligning the periodicity of attracted funds and assets and increasing the share of high-quality assets with minimal mandatory reserve requirements set by the Central Bank [3].

A. Axmedov, in his doctoral dissertation, develops scientific proposals and recommendations to enhance asset efficiency through asset protection. He suggests increasing asset efficiency through securitization, specifically by issuing securities based on bank loans to attract funds. This mechanism allows for transferring credit risks to other financial institutions, thereby creating conditions to ensure the financial stability of commercial banks [4].

Sh. Baxriddinov, in his doctoral dissertation, systematizes theoretical approaches to effective asset management. He notes that effective asset management ensures maximum returns within acceptable risk levels and facilitates the optimization of the structure of liabilities. From this perspective, asset efficiency should increase net income, enhance non-interest income, reduce non-interest expenses, improve the structure of bank loans, and enhance liquidity [5]. Capital profitability is also a critical indicator, reflecting how effectively a bank utilizes its own funds. This indicator highlights the importance of capital profitability in the operations of commercial banks.

G. Pennacchi and J. Santos analyze why banks use the capital profitability category to assess and evaluate their operational profitability. They note that since the 1970s, banks have shifted from using Earnings Per Share to ROE. They analyze how banks choose capital in the context of strict deposit insurance and increasing competitive conditions, which enables a more accurate assessment of efficiency. However, they point out that increased regulatory demands for bank stability may reduce the likelihood of using the ROE indicator [6].

J. Karr questions the reliance on capital profitability in banking operations. He indicates that macroeconomic instability and increasing pressure on bank capital reduce its effectiveness. According to him, the shortcomings of capital profitability include its inability to reflect long-term stability, seasonal influences, manipulative situations, or positive trends under stress conditions. He suggests using Risk-Adjusted Return on Capital and isolating asset and capital quality indicators (e.g., NPL). Additionally, he emphasizes evaluating factors such as profitability (Return on RWA, tangible equity), efficiency (cost-to-income, cost-of-equity), asset quality (NPL), and income structure (recurring/volatility) [7].

It should be noted that some foreign studies suggest that capital profitability cannot serve as the primary factor in reflecting bank stability. This indicates that capital profitability may not fully manifest in certain cases due to increased pressure on bank capital and macroeconomic instability. Therefore, macroeconomic conditions and information asymmetry are critical for ensuring banks' financial stability.

Overall, some studies question whether capital profitability is a reality or a myth. S. Moussu and A. Petit-Romec analyze the role of capital profitability as a central indicator. They note that this indicator is a key figure reflecting the efficiency of the banking sector but can falsely influence stock prices before a crisis. They also highlight that the financial bonuses tied to bank

management's results increase risk appetite, recommending that bank management and regulators avoid overemphasizing capital profitability [8].

In our view, the capital profitability indicator cannot assess a bank's susceptibility to extreme risk situations. Therefore, analyzing capital profitability while considering simulation scenarios is advisable.

Overall, the instability of capital profitability is observed to be tied to macroeconomic conditions. For instance, Figure 1 illustrates the trends in capital profitability in the European Union banking sector from 2007 to 2023. The data shows a sharp decline in capital profitability during the 2008-2009 financial crisis, indicating challenges for the banking sector during 2008-2012. From 2013 to 2019, stable growth was observed, with ROE rising from -1.57% to 5.38%. However, the 2020 pandemic caused a decline in capital efficiency, though post-pandemic recovery saw ROE increase from 2.31% to 9.29% between 2021 and 2023 (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Capital Profitability in the EU Banking Sector, 2007-2023 [9]

In our opinion, the EU experience shows that bank capital profitability is linked to macroeconomic conditions, reflecting the high sensitivity of banks' financial stability to external factors. Therefore, considering both macro and microeconomic trends is crucial for ensuring financial stability in bank management.

The issue is that aligning the risk appetite of bank shareholders and management in managing capital profitability can lead to increased bank instability.

M. Alhadab and Bassam Al-Own, in their joint study analyzing European banks' performance from 2001 to 2015, assess the management of capital profitability. They evaluate the short- and long-term impacts of discretionary credit loss reserves. An increase in credit risk reserves leads to a decline in profitability, with effects lasting up to five years, putting pressure on capital profitability [10].

In another study by S. Moussu and A. Petit-Romec, they address whether capital profitability serves as a performance indicator or a risk measure during crises. Higher capital profitability in large banks is associated with greater losses during crises. They note that while

capital profitability is a performance indicator, it also serves as a risk measure, particularly during crises, and can enable risk management by increasing the risk appetite of bank management and shareholders [11].

In our research, we aim to analyze the financial indicators of JSC “Aloqabank” from January 2019 to April 2025. The selected database is based on the bank’s monthly reports, covering balance sheets and financial performance reports. Our analysis begins by examining the impact of balance sheet indicators, such as Tier 1 and Tier 2 capital volumes and the leverage ratio.

Table 1. Average Values of JSC “Aloqabank” Financial Indicators, 2019-2025

Indicator Name	Mean	Std. Err.
Balance Sheet Indicators		
Cash and other payment documents	3.51e+08	2.01e+07
Net receivables from other banks and financial institutions	7.94e+08	5.13e+07
Net loans and leasing operations	8.10e+09	3.00e+08
Demand deposits	2.00e+09	1.08e+08
Term deposits	5.17e+09	2.33e+08
Tax liabilities	6706194	1790311
Undistributed profits	3.83e+08	2.87e+07
Bank Income		
Total interest income	7.95e+08	5.71e+07
Interest income from other banks	1.45e+07	1266831
Interest and discount income from loans and leasing	6.48e+08	5.14e+07
Total interest expenses	5.76e+08	4.53e+07
Interest expenses on deposits	4.38e+08	3.98e+07
Interest expenses on loans and other liabilities	1.34e+08	1.03e+07
Total non-interest income	3.96e+08	4.43e+07
Income from services and intermediation	2.25e+08	2.31e+07
Foreign currency profits	5.63e+07	5556189
Total non-interest expenses	1.90e+08	2.07e+07
Expenses for intermediation and services	1.52e+08	1.79e+07
Foreign currency losses	3.42e+07	3225815
Total operating expenses	2.14e+08	1.84e+07
Financial Stability Indicators		
Tier 1 core capital	1.67e+09	7.12e+07
Total Tier 2 capital	2.51e+08	2.35e+07
Leverage ratio	12.63132	.3512107
Available stable funding	8.16e+09	3.69e+08
Required stable funding	7.63e+09	3.96e+08

ROA (Return on Assets)	2.060263	.1192735
ROE (Return on Equity)	13.55461	2.564102
Regulatory capital to risk-weighted assets	15.73039	.2966952
Interest margin to gross income	36.97421	1.400615
Liquid assets to total assets	15.71421	.4329602

Overall, we believe that evaluating the impact of JSC “Aloqabank”’s own funds and liabilities, as reflected in its balance sheet, on financial stability indicators Serves to develop scientifically grounded proposals and recommendations. Table 1 presents trends reflecting the bank’s balance sheet and income. Additionally, statistical data on related variables such as capital, its adequacy, liquidity, leverage, and profitability can be observed. We plan to conduct these analyses using the Stata software package.

Table 2. Dickey-Fuller Test for JSC “Aloqabank” Balance Sheet Indicators

Variable	Z(t)	P-Value	Stationarity Level
Tier 1 core capital	0.792	0.9915	✗ I(1) (non-stationary)
Total Tier 2 capital	-0.882	0.7940	✗ I(1)
Leverage ratio	-2.910	0.0442	✓ I(0) — stationary
Cash and other payment documents	-1.463	0.5518	✗ I(1)
Net receivables from other banks and financial institutions	-0.593	0.8727	✗ I(1)
Net loans and leasing operations	1.258	0.9964	✗ I(1)
Demand deposits	0.536	0.9859	✗ I(1)
Term deposits	3.326	1.0000	✗ I(1)
Tax liabilities	-3.626	0.0053	✓ I(0) — stationary
Undistributed profits	-2.128	0.2333	✗ I(1)

We begin by conducting econometric studies to identify and evaluate the impact of balance sheet indicators on bank capital and leverage ratios. Table 2 presents the stationarity test results. As seen, tax liabilities are stationary, while the remaining indicators are non-stationary. These test results enable the selection of the ARDL (AutoRegressive Distributed Lag) model due to the presence or absence of stationarity.

Table 3 presents data from the ARDL(1,1,2,1,1,1,0,2) regression model covering the period from January 2019 to April 2025. The model includes 72 total observations. With an R-squared of 0.9375 and an adjusted R-squared of 0.9193, the model explains the essence of Tier 1 capital with high accuracy. Additionally, the F-test (Prob > F = 0.0000) indicates the high statistical significance of the overall model.

Based on the statistical significance of the selected indicators in Table 3, we formulated the following scientific conclusions:

1. The impact of changes in financial resources related to cash and other payment documents is not statistically significant.

2. Changes in the amount of receivables from other banks and financial institutions are statistically significant at lag 2. Given its negative impact, an increase in receivables from other banks leads to a decrease in Tier 1 capital after two months.

3. The impact of changes in loans and leasing operations and tax liabilities is not statistically significant, indicating no effect.

4. Demand deposits show a slight statistically significant impact at lag 1, suggesting that funds held until demanded can be used as capital. However, many studies recommend against using such funds as capital.

5. Term deposits have a strong impact at lag 1, indicating that an increase in deposits positively affects the bank's capital and has immediate significance.

6. Undistributed profits have a strong and highly statistically significant impact at lags 1 and 2, reflecting their high economic importance.

Table 3. ARDL Model for Factors Affecting Tier 1 Capital

Sample	2019m5 - 2025m4	Number of obs	72
F(16, 55)	51.52	R-squared	0.9375
Prob > F	0.0000	Adj R-squared	0.9193
Log likelihood	-1459.7328	Root MSE	1.767e+08

Tier 1 Capital	Coefficient	Std. err.	t	P>t	[95% conf. interval]	interval]
Tier 1 Capital						
L1.	-.0084269	.1201517	-0.07	0.944	-.2492163	.2323626
Cash and other payment documents						
-.	.159901	.3137208	0.51	0.612	-.4688096	.7886115
L1.	.4767275	.3068909	1.55	0.126	-.1382956	1.091751
Net receivables from other banks and financial institutions						
-.	.1396723	.0914518	1.53	0.132	-.0436013	.3229458
L1.	-.0446075	.097106	-0.46	0.648	-.2392122	.1499972
L2.	-.1818797	.0879737	-2.07	0.043	-.3581829	-.005576
Net loans and leasing operations						
-.	-.0046877	.1362537	-0.03	0.973	-.2777463	.2683708
L1.	-.2099446	.1345575	-1.56	0.124	-.4796039	.0597146
Demand deposits						
-.	.0989943	.1491627	0.66	0.510	-.1999345	.3979231
L1.	.2805	.1543548	1.82	0.075	-.0288339	.589834
Term deposits						
-.	.0277964	.0946141	0.29	0.770	-.1618145	.2174074

L1.	.3187141	.1011435	3.15	0.003	.1160181	.5214101
Tax liabilities	.2769563	1.621653	0.17	0.865	-2.972909	3.526822
Undistributed profits						
-.	.3435475	.1942007	1.77	0.082	-.0456394	.7327344
L1.	1.00132	.2658412	3.77	0.000	.468562	1.534077
L2.	-.5740528	.1970974	-2.91	0.005	-.9690448	-.179060
_cons	4.23e+08	1.52e+08	2.79	0.007	1.19e+08	7.27e+08

Conclusion

In conclusion, the efficiency of bank capital and assets plays a significant role in ensuring the financial stability of banks. Considering financial performance indicators alongside macroeconomic stability is advisable. Therefore, ensuring banks' financial stability involves maintaining a financial balance to prevent an increase in the risk exposure of assets as capital profitability rises.

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